

A novel aptamer-based approach for detecting a target microorganism in soil

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Abstract

The uncertainty associated with the impact of a bioinoculant on soil microbial community and, as a consequence, on soil quality, as well as the need to define its persistence, has prompted the demand for an accurate detection and tracking system of the presence and the quantification of a target microbial inoculant in soil. Although DNA or RNA-based molecular detection are well established and commonly applied in this regard, alternative ligands such as DNA-aptamers have several advantages over them, such as low cost, ease of modification, ease of immobilisation on lab-on-chip or nanosensors, high chemical and thermal stability. In this study, we used a toggle-cell SELEX method to isolate, select and characterize ssDNA (single-strand DNA) aptamers to detect a *Bacillus subtilis* strain which is being tested as a plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) formulation. Two ssDNA aptamers (patent application n.102022000022590) showed strong affinity and specificity for *B. subtilis* strains, with values of the kinetic parameters K_d (dissociation constant) and B_{max} (maximum intensity of binding) in the nanomolar range and around 1, respectively. Aptamers suitability was validated on three inoculated soils characterized by different chemical-physical features and in soil from a field trial with the formulated *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 strain. Aptamers proved to be an efficient tool to monitor a strain-specific bacteria in soil, applicable in the optimisation of bioinoculants use and suitable to support the registration processes of these products.

Keywords: DNA aptamer, *B. subtilis*, detection, soil

INTRODUCTION

Microorganisms are essential components of bio-based agricultural means of production like biofertilisers and biopesticides (Macik et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 2018; Malusà et al., 2016). The use of these products has gained attention from researchers, manufacturers, and farmers due to their potential to reduce the reliance on chemical inputs in agriculture (Belmans et al., 2018). Despite the expected increase in their application, specific challenges related to their effectiveness and interaction with native soil microorganisms hinder their widespread use (Malusà et al., 2021). Detection and tracking microbial inoculants in soil are crucial to assess their impact on soil quality and efficacy. Conventional detection methods such as cultural enrichment, plating, and DNA-based techniques are time-consuming and expensive. Therefore, developing a rapid, precise, and species-specific detection tool is essential to foster bioinoculants use. Nanoscale biosensors are a cost-effective and compelling solution for detecting microbial species in complex environmental samples. They offer sensitivity, specificity, and portability, making them ideal for rapid detection. Aptamers, i.e. single-strand oligonucleotides with high affinity for specific target molecules, present promising characteristics for developing nanoscale biosensors. *Bacillus* includes well-known plant-growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) species, some of which are widely used as bioinoculants. Monitoring and tracking specific species or strains within this genus can significantly optimise bioinoculant application. This paper reports on the development of two aptamers for detecting a strain of *B. subtilis* (PCM/B 00105), which is being tested as a PGPR.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Bacterial isolation

B. subtilis PCM/B00105 was isolated from the commercial product BACTIM, with a ten-fold serial dilution in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) up to dilution 10^{-7} . The dilutions were plated in duplicates on Trypticase Soy Agar (TSA) and then incubated at 30°C for 24-48 h.

DNA extraction and sanger sequencing of bacterial isolates

DNA extraction of the cultured isolates was carried out using the Quick-DNA Fungal/Bacterial kit. DNA crude extract yields were measured using the Qubit® 2.0 Fluorometer. The 16S rRNA gene of the isolated DNA was amplified using the primers 63-F and 1087-R, and the PCR products were evaluated by 1% agarose gel electrophoresis. Samples were then purified and subjected to DNA Sanger sequencing. The sequences of the isolates were compared with the NCBI sequence database for identification and as verification of the correct isolation of the strain.

Next-generation sequencing

Next-generation sequencing of *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 was performed to obtain a complete genome of the strain. The sequencing was performed using the Celero™ DNA-Seq kit for library preparation (kit used by the sequencing service). The resulting library was then sequenced on Illumina NovaSeq 6000 in paired-end 150 mode, producing 10+10 million reads. The Illumina reads were assembled with SPAdes v3.14.1 (Bankevich et al., 2012) and polished with BWA mem v0.7.17 (Li and Durbin, 2010) and pilon v1.23 (Walker et al., 2014). Genes were predicted and analyzed using RAST from the web interface using the Classic RAST (<https://rast.nmpdr.org/>) annotation scheme (Aziz et al., 2008), and FIGfam releases 70 (<https://www.theseed.org/wiki/Glossary#FIGfam>). The genome of *B. subtilis* was predicted and analyzed using Artemis 4.0 software (Carver et al., 2012), and deposited (BioProject: PRJNA902951).

Pangenome analysis

A pangenomic analysis using 512 sequences of *Bacillus* species obtained from the NCBI's GenBank facility was conducted to identify sequences in specific regions of the *B. subtilis* genome suitable for aptamer design. The genomes were annotated with Prokka (Seemann, 2014), and the pangenome was calculated using Roary v3.13.0 (Page et al., 2015). The results were visualized with a Python script (roary_plots.py) (https://github.com/sanger-pathogens/Roary/tree/master/contrib/roary_plots).

Sequential toggle cell (STC)-SELEX process

The SELEX process (Song et al., 2017) for selecting suitable aptamers was applied using a random single-strand DNA (ssDNA) library and primers for PCR. The *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 was cultured overnight from a single colony in a different liquid medium. The cells were then subcultured to reach approximately 1×10^8 colony-forming unit (CFU) mL⁻¹. The cultured bacteria were recovered, washed, and resuspended in 1 mL of binding buffer for the STC-SELEX process.

Bacterial cell extraction from soil

Soil microcosms (100-mL jar), using three soils differing for the main physical-chemical parameters were prepared to assess the aptamers capacity to detect the *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 in situ. The soils were characterized as silty clay soil with alkaline pH (from Italy), sandy soil with neutral pH (from Poland and medium textured sandy loam soil with sub-alkaline pH (from Germany). The complete physico-chemical characterization of the three soils is presented in Manfredini et al. (2023a). Each soil was autoclaved for 30 min at 121°C and incubated for 24 h at 30°C; then, the process was repeated four times. After the process, a small aliquot (1 g) was sampled in sterile mode, resuspended in 9 mL of physiological solution and plated onto Trypticase soy agar (TSA), (CM0131B, Oxoid, Thermo Fisher

Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) to verify the absence of bacterial growth. Subsequently, a *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 suspension was prepared at a concentration of 0.5 MCFU (McFarland unit equal to 1.5×10^8 CFU mL⁻¹). Then the soils (40 g) were inoculated with 1 mL of bacterial suspension. The microcosms were incubated at 30°C for 12 days, and every two days, the humidity was checked and restored if necessary. After 12 days, 1 g of soil was collected from each microcosm, to which 9 mL of sodium pyrophosphate was added to favor the detachment of the cells from the soil particles. One hundred microliter of standard aptamer 1 and 2 (from 0 to 250 nM) was added for each aliquot. A method for extracting cells from the soil was also developed based on the one proposed by Ouyang et al. (2021), with particular attention to clayey soil, which required the application of an ad hoc protocol. Briefly, the soils were subjected to agitation at 200 counts per minute (cpm) and subsequently filtered by a cell strainer with a mesh size of 100 µm (Clear Line, Biosigma S.p.A., Cone, IT).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of 512 *Bacillus* genomes identified a total of 35172 gene families, including 8866 core genes (25.2% of the total), 4334 accessory genes (12.3%), and 2109 singletons (5.9%). The pangenome analysis identified a unique trait/oligonucleotide sequence (data under patenting process), which was used to design primer pairs for constructing ssDNA aptamers libraries. The primer pairs have been claimed in the patent application n—102022000022590 to the Italian Patent Office and submitted also to the European Union Patent Office. The SELEX process started with a library of random ssDNA fragments to isolate aptamers (Song et al., 2017). Five rounds were carried out to obtain the desired ssDNA yield, resulting in 140 clones. After sequencing analysis, 25 different ssDNA sequences were identified, with two sequences, Apta1 and Apta2, selected for further affinity analysis. The secondary structures of Apta1 and Apta2 showed a bulb-like stem-loop structure. The binding affinity of these two aptamers to five bacteria species was assessed (Dwivedi et al., 2010, 2013). Both aptamers preferentially bound to *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105. Apta1 showed higher specificity and was deemed the best candidate for detecting *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 in soil. Apta2 displayed a high binding affinity also to a different strain of *B. subtilis*. The minimum and maximum binding concentrations for both aptamers were determined. The K_d of both aptamers with the target strain was much lower than in other studies (Figure 1). The aptamers shared a core sequence and exhibited a secondary structure allowing them to bind to the target cells.

To validate the results obtained in vitro, an experiment with soils inoculated with a formulation containing the *B. subtilis* PCM/B 00105 strain was carried out. The method of extracting the cells from soil samples was necessary to be optimised due to impurities and interferences of soil compounds and texture affecting extraction efficiency (Manfredini et al., 2023b). The soil's physical-chemical characteristics affected the bacteria cell yield after extraction, with sandy soil yielding the highest number of cells. The detection capacity of the aptamers was verified one week after inoculation, showing that soils with higher organic matter and clay exhibited the highest values of kinetic parameters for both aptamers.

CONCLUSIONS

The study described a method for selecting DNA-based aptamers targeting a specific bacteria strain used as PGPR and the possibility to detect the strain when inoculated in soil without nucleic acid isolation. The work identified two species-specific ssDNA aptamers with high binding capacity to a *B. subtilis* strain of a commercial formulation. Optimisation of the cell extraction procedure from soils was necessary to validate the aptamer detection capacity of the specific strain from lab and field soil samples. The development of a lab-on-chip device based on these aptamers could support bioinocula application and regulatory processes, essential for sustainable cropping systems.

Figure 1. Binding saturation curve of the two selected aptamers (A) and comparison of the binding intensity of Apt1 with that of random ssDNA to each tested bacteria species (B). RFU is the relative fluorescence unit used in analyses employing fluorescence detection.

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